

**AWARENESS ON THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE
IN HEALTHCARE SYSTEMS IN BENUE STATE UNIVERSITY TEACHING
HOSPITAL (BSUTH), MAKURDI.**

By

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ABSTRACT

This research work investigates the “Awareness on the use of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare Systems in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi”. A descriptive survey design was adopted to evaluate the current state of healthcare system, to identify areas where Artificial Intelligence (AI) can enhance efficiency and patient care, to determine the techniques involved in the adoption of Artificial Intelligence for health care, to assess the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications on patient care outcomes and satisfaction. A total of 1433 Staff selected from five (5) Departments in the surveyed hospital and a sample size of 320 was determined using Solvin’s Formula with the aid of Stratified Random Sampling Technique. A well-structured close-ended questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. Four research questions guided the study. The researcher used frequency and mean to analyze the data. Taking the conclusion into consideration, the researcher recommend that Management of health institution should inject more financial resources into the organization in order to adopt the use of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare Systems to enhance the quality, efficiency, and accessibility of services. The government/management should ensure adequate continues professional development, collaboration and partnership. They should always ensure adequate training/re-training of staff on the advancement of the ever-changing technological world in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi.

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence (AI) is one of the most revolutionary technological advancements to emerge in recent times that is remodeling and shaping the world. AI has the propensity of making impossibilities of the past possible. With the advent of AI technology, there will be continual discovery of new possibilities and opportunities. The field of AI dates back to 1956 at a workshop at Dartmouth College where the terminology AI was first postulated by John Mc Carthy.

At present, in every aspect of human endeavour, AI has played a substantial role in the perception, processing, and interpretation of information. AI, also known as machine intelligence, is the ability of machines to demonstrate intelligence likened to that exhibited by humans. No wonder, it is also often referred to as machines' ability to demonstrate cognitive function which is associated with human thought. With AI, machines now interpret, analyze, and process complex data systems in a variety of applications, including web search, self-driving vehicles, and computer vision and most especially in healthcare.

A study conducted by BBC at Oxford revealed that AI could lead to 40% of jobs loss in Europe within 10 years whereas up to half of jobs will be lost in the USA, and to a greater degree in the developing parts of the world. Technological advancement has contributed immensely to global economic dominance and power by the advanced economies. This will eventually make the developing economy to be more and more dependents on the developed economy. A research published by the Accenture Institute for High Performance posited that by 2035, AI will lead to very rapid yearly economic growth in the developed world. According to a New York-based innovation business visionary Jack Hidary, he said that AI will be of great advantage by improving the quality of lives of the world's poor economy.

A Vanguard publication in 2019 documented that since the inception of the concept of AI, most developed countries have keyed into its application; however, its concept is still not very familiar with many Nigerians. This report is similar to that obtained in other developing economy. An information and communication technology (ICT) expert mentioned in that report that this is the apt time for Nigeria as a nation need to key into the concept of AI like other developed countries and utilize the opportunities therein. Adding that, most people in Nigeria still perceive AI as a fiction of science that will rule the world and replace the jobs done by humans; however, contrary to that perception, the ICT expert documented with optimism that AI will not replace humans. Vanguard publication (2019).

The application of AI in the health industry has been of immense contribution to the quality of healthcare. It is documented that AI application is involved drug discovery, medical diagnosis, routine patient monitoring, and risk management. Notwithstanding there are some challenges regarding the implementation of this technology, it is believed that AI application will save more lives and improve lives by revolutionizing the inefficient healthcare delivery systems.

It is employed in various fields of medicine including ophthalmology, surgery, pathology, dermatology, and ophthalmology, as well as hospital management. According to a recent study in Children's National Medical Centre in Washington (2022), a robot successfully performed an open surgery under the supervision of a team of surgeons, and the most interesting aspect is

the acceptance of the team of surgeons that the surgery performed by the robot was better than that performed by human surgeons. Studies have revealed that AI is capable to precisely making diagnose as good as well-trained medical personnel for cancer of the skin, monitor patients at high risk of cancer, and perform ophthalmologic diagnosis within 30 seconds.

AI is seen as the best way to understand the pattern of disease spread, as well as provide support to patients. The future of AI is advancing to distinguish the cause of infection, find the cure for disease, envisage a possible outbreak, and also predict the possible area of the outbreak, all with very negligible human input. These were evident by the use of AI technology in the management of the Ebola virus in the past.

AI services have been rendered in the healthcare sector recently. According to Agarwal et al. (2020), artificial intelligence and robotic surgery allow practitioners to facilitate patients in personalized healthcare, decrease repetitive tasks, and move forward to prevent serious illness. The recent development in machine learning and artificial intelligence provides personalized care without the patient's differences. Chen et al.(2019) study machine learning and artificial intelligence findings, evaluating and distinguishing different artificial intelligence effects in healthcare and using a machine learning algorithm on unstructured clinical and psychiatric explanations to calculate an intensive care unit (ICU) death according to Wartman and Combs (2019), Confusing this excess data disaster between apprentices is the circumstance that doctors' skill sets now must include cooperating with and dealing with artificial intelligence (AI) applications.

Recent advancements in artificial intelligence have brought about significant progress within hospital environments. The integration of AI and machine learning in healthcare and health informatics is aiding healthcare providers in enhancing diagnostic precision and predicting potential high-risk conditions. Additionally, AI is contributing to the customization of patient care by providing doctors with valuable insights into patterns of symptoms and effective treatment strategies, ultimately improving patient outcomes. According to David and Agus (2019), AI enables the exploration of data on health conditions in greater depth, uncovering associations that may be beyond the capacity of the human brain but well-suited for computational analysis.

Finally, it is intended to guide the companies, universities, medical associations and international organizations that will, with governments and ministries of health, set policies and practices to define use of AI in the health sector. In identifying the many ethical concerns raised by AI and by providing the relevant ethical frameworks to address such concerns, this document is intended to support responsible use of AI worldwide. WHO recognizes that AI is a fast-moving, evolving field and that many applications, not yet envisaged, will emerge as ever-greater public and private investment is dedicated to the use of AI for health. For example, in 2020, WHO issued interim guidance on the use of proximity tracking applications intended to facilitate contact-tracing during the COVID-19 pandemic. WHO may consider specific guidance for additional tools and applications and periodically update this guidance to keep pace with this rapidly changing field. It is therefore pertinent to evaluate the application of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare System in BSUTH, Makurdi.

1.1 STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Artificial Intelligence (AI), has been playing a vital and growing role in the world in the past few decades. In fact, many people do not realize the form in which artificial intelligence can present itself in their daily life. When logging into email accounts, shopping using online platforms, requesting for car riding services, etc., all these uses artificial intelligence algorithms to improve user experience. And, the most important field where AI is growing rapidly in the medical field, especially in treatment management and diagnostic. This has created tension of Artificial Intelligence surpassing human tasks and ability. Several research papers have shown that in future Artificial Intelligence can support human judgment, aid in clinical decisions, and increase treatment efficiency. In 2014, the AI sector in the United States was valued at about \$600 million, showing that it is one of the highest growth industries in the world.

Today, Artificial Intelligence is greatly used in many healthcare centres in the world since it has simplified the lives of patients and doctors by performing complex and important tasks in less time and at a fraction of the cost, and higher precision. Therefore, AI has countless applications in healthcare that is, from finding links between genetic codes to driving robots used in surgery process. In fact, it is reinventing, and it has been a boon, to the healthcare industry. The growth of AI in healthcare relates to the complexities of modern medicines which requires a copious amount of information to analyse, and also there are limited numbers of clinicians to handle with human intelligence.

Due to this, AI applications have been using advanced computing to overcome human intelligence limitations in the medical field using several techniques to assist clinicians in healthcare centres. One of the common techniques is the use of expert systems that are based on rules which outlines the steps involved in transforming the inputs into actionable outputs. In view of that artificial intelligence in the health care sector in Nigeria is still under developed; as Nigeria is currently one of the Nations on the third-world list of developing countries in the technological field. Unlike the developed Nations like USA, where AI in the healthcare sector has grown strong and has been helping to boost the Nation's health care sector. Nigeria is still backward. This research study will identify the application and opportunities of Artificial Intelligence on health care in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi.

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The main objective of the research is to investigate into the Awareness on the use of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare Systems in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi and the specific objectives are:

- i. To evaluate the current state of healthcare system in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi.
- ii. To identify areas where Artificial Intelligence (AI) can enhance efficiency and patient care in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi.
- iii. To determine the techniques involved in the adoption of Artificial Intelligence for health care systems in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi.
- iv. To assess the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications on patient care outcomes and satisfaction in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi.

1.3 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

- i. What are the current state of healthcare system in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi?
- ii. What are the areas where Artificial Intelligence (AI) can enhance efficiency and patient care in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi?
- iii. What are the techniques involved in the adoption of Artificial Intelligence for health care systems in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi?
- iv. What are the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications on patient care outcomes and satisfaction in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi?

1.4 SCOPE OF STUDY

This research is limited to the Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi; comprising Health information management department, Pharmacy department, Medical Doctors department, Nurses department, and Laboratory department on the awareness on the use of artificial intelligence in healthcare delivery system.

1.5 SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

The research in identifying the Awareness on the use of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare Delivery System in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi will be beneficial to health care workers and the hospital management. It will also be beneficial to stakeholders in Nigeria's health care sector. Lastly, it will be beneficial as it will help serving as a foundation upon which further researches can be conducted.

2. METHODOLOGY

This project is on the awareness on the use of artificial intelligence in healthcare systems in benue state university teaching hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi.

2.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

The systematic research design used in this study is the descriptive study techniques using survey method. This study method involved questionnaire.

2.2 POPULATION OF THE STUDY

The study area covers the Health Information Management Professional, Doctors, Nurses, Pharmacy and Medical Laboratory Scientist of Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital which is estimated at 1,433 staff.

2.3 SAMPLE SIZE AND SAMPLING TECHNIQUES

With regards to the fact that this research study focuses on the integrity and validity of Health Information in Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital among Doctors, Nurses, Pharmacy, Medical Laboratory Scientist and Health Information Management Professional. The sampling method was simple random sampling, the researcher decided to use Health Information Management Professional 130, Medical Doctors 223, Nurses 934, Pharmacy 71 and Medical Laboratory Scientist 75, and a sample size of 320 was determined using Solvin's Formula.

given as:

$$n = N / 1 + N(e)^2$$

Where n=sample size

$$N = \text{population} = 1433$$

$$e = \text{level of significance} = 0.05$$

$$n = 1433 / 1 + 1433 (0.05)^2$$

$$= 1433 / 4.485$$

$$= 320$$

The sampling techniques deployed for this research is the stratified random sampling technique, is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller group called strata. The selection of respondents for each professional was done using proportional allocation as follows.

Proportional stratification: $n = nN_h$

n - Represent the total number of population each strata

N_h - Represent the total population the researcher to sample out of the total population.

N - Represent the total of the population the research will be applied.

n_1 – Medical Doctors

$$= 223 \times 320 / 1433$$

$$= 50$$

n_2 - Nurses

$$= 934 \times 320 / 1433$$

$$= 208$$

n_3 - Pharmacist

$$= 71 \times 320 / 1433$$

$$= 16$$

n_4 — Medical Laboratory Scientist

$$= 75 \times 320 / 1433$$

$$= 17$$

n_5 - Health Information Management

$$= 130 \times 320 / 1433$$

$$= 29$$

$$n = n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + n_4 + n_5$$

$$n = 50 + 208 + 16 + 17 + 29$$

$$n = 320$$

2.4 RESEARCH INSTRUMENT

The instrument use for data collection in this research work was a well-structured questionnaire containing close ended questions which enables the researcher to collect the data appropriate, three hundred and twenty (320) questionnaire were distributed to Doctors, Nurses, Pharmacy, Medical Laboratory Scientist and Health Information Professionals.

2.5 Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

The content validity was determined by giving the project supervisor and expert in the field to check whether it will test what it supposed to measure the instrument is in line with the objectives and the research questions. To ensure reliability the questionnaire was pre-test using 10 students at an interval of one week and the result is similar this means that the instrument was reliable.

2.6 Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher personally distributed 320 questionnaires to Doctors, Nurses, Pharmacy, Medical Laboratory Scientist and the staff of Health Information Management. And only a day was given to the respondents to fill the questionnaire after which the researcher collects the questionnaire at the end of the day.

2.7 Method of Data Analysis

For the purpose of this study and to achieve accuracy in processing the data collected, the researcher used frequency and mean to analyze the data.

3. PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS OF FINDINGS

Tables and charts would be used to present findings. Data collected would be analyzed according to the nature of responses.

3.1 DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION OF RESPONDENTS

TABLE 1: GENDER OF RESPONDENTS

Gender	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Male	190	63%
Female	112	37%
Total	302	100%

Table 1 above shows that majority 63% of the respondents were Male, while 37% of them were Female.

TABLE 2: AGE OF RESPONDENTS

Age Range	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Below 25yrs	11	4%
25-34yrs	91	30%
35-44yrs	130	43%
45yrs and above	70	23%
Total	302	100%

Table above shows that majority 43% of the respondents were between the age range of 35-44yrs, 30% were between 25-34yrs, 23% were 45yrs and above, while 4% were below 25yrs.

TABLE 3: EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATIONS OF RESPONDENTS

Qualification	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
ND	120	40%
B.Sc/HND	92	30%
Post Graduate	60	20%
Others	30	10%
Total	302	100%

Table above shows that majority 40% of the respondents are ND holders, 30% are B.Sc/HND holders, 20% are Post Graduate holders, while 10% goes for other qualifications.

TABLE 4: PROFESSION OF RESPONDENTS

Profession	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
HIM	29	10%
Nurses	190	63%
Doctors	51	17%
Pharmacist	16	5%
Lab. Scientists	16	5%
Total	302	100%

Table above shows that majority 63% of the respondents are Nurses, 17% are Doctors, 10% are from HIM profession, and 5% are Lab. Scientists, and also 5% are Pharmacists.

TABLE 5: WORKING EXPERIENCE OF RESPONDENTS

Years of Experience	Frequency (f)	Percentage (%)
Below 5 years	161	53%
5-10 years	90	30%
11 years and above	51	17%
Total	302	100%

Table above shows that majority 53% of the respondents falls below 5 years of working experience, and 30% of them are between 5-10 years of experience, while 17% has 11 years and above working experience.

Table 6: The current state of the Healthcare System in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi.

Question	SA (5)	A (4)	D (3)	SD (2)	UD (1)	Mean (X)

Healthcare services are easily accessible to all members of community	101	195	6	0	0	4.31
There are enough healthcare facilities and resources to meet the demand	75	193	20	11	3	4.07
Patients generally trust their healthcare providers and feel respected during medical consultations	111	185	2	4	0	4.33
Technological advancements, such as electronic health records and telemedicine, improve patient care	222	80	0	0	0	4.73

The table above shows the current state of the Healthcare System in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi, represented by their means (\bar{X}); Healthcare services are easily accessible to all members of community (4.31), There are enough healthcare facilities and resources to meet the demand (4.07), Patients generally trust their healthcare providers and feel respected during medical consultations (4.33), while majority of the respondents agrees that, technological advancements, such as electronic health records and telemedicine, improve patient care (4.73).

Table 7: The areas where Artificial Intelligence (AI) can enhance efficiency and patient care in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi.

Question	SA (5)	A (4)	D (3)	SD (2)	UD (1)	Mean (\bar{X})
AI help improve diagnosis accuracy by analyzing medical images, such as X-rays and MRIs	170	50	35	40	7	4.09
AI is capable of identifying patterns in patient data to assist healthcare providers in making more informed treatment decisions	36	174	69	18	5	3.71
AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants help streamline administrative tasks and improve patient communication	88	150	56	8	0	4.05
AI-driven decision support systems help reduce medical errors and improve patient safety	112	190	0	0	0	4.37
AI is capable of automating repetitive tasks in healthcare, such as transcription and documentation, to save time for healthcare professionals	155	185	48	4	10	4.62

Table 7 above shows areas where Artificial Intelligence (AI) can enhance efficiency and patient care in Benue State University Teaching Hospital (BSUTH), Makurdi, represented by

their means (\bar{X}); AI help improve diagnosis accuracy by analyzing medical images, such as X-rays and MRIs (4.09), AI is capable of identifying patterns in patient data to assist healthcare providers in making more informed treatment decisions (3.71), AI-powered chat bots and virtual assistants help streamline administrative tasks and improve patient communication (4.05), AI-driven decision support systems help reduce medical errors and improve patient safety (4.37), while majority of the respondents with mean 4.62, represent AI is capable of automating repetitive tasks in healthcare, such as transcription and documentation, to save time for healthcare professionals.

Table 8: The techniques involved in the adoption of Artificial Intelligence for healthcare systems.

Question	SA (5)	A (4)	D (3)	SD (2)	UD (1)	Mean (\bar{X})
Your healthcare organization implemented AI-powered algorithms to analyze medical images (e.g., X-rays, MRIs) for diagnosis and treatment planning	100	200	2	0	0	4.32
The adoption of Artificial Intelligence has the potential to significantly transform and improve healthcare delivery in various aspects of your organization	192	80	15	5	10	5.77
Your organization adopted AI for automating repetitive tasks such as transcription and documentation, thereby saving time for healthcare professionals	50	200	7	25	20	3.71
AI-driven decision support systems are implemented to assist healthcare providers in making more informed clinical decisions and reducing medical errors	160	70	15	50	7	3.61
AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants are being employed to automate administrative tasks and improve patient communication within your healthcare system	161	95	46	0	0	4.38

Table 8 above shows the techniques involved in the adoption of Artificial Intelligence for healthcare systems, represented by their means (\bar{X}); Your healthcare organization implemented AI-powered algorithms to analyze medical images (e.g., X-rays, MRIs) for diagnosis and treatment planning (4.32), majority of the respondents agree that adoption of Artificial Intelligence has the potential to significantly transform and improve healthcare delivery in various aspects of your organization (5.77), Your organization adopted AI for automating repetitive tasks such as transcription and documentation, thereby saving time for healthcare professionals (3.71), AI-driven decision support systems are implemented to assist healthcare providers in making more informed clinical decisions and reducing medical errors (3.61), while AI-powered chatbots and virtual assistants are being employed to automate administrative tasks and improve patient communication within your healthcare system (4.38).

Table 9: The impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications on patient care outcomes and satisfaction.

Question	SA (5)	A (4)	D (3)	SD (2)	UD (1)	Mean (\bar{X})
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Patients benefit from more accurate and timely diagnoses	194	70	0	18	20	4.50
AI-enabled personalized medicine contributed to better patient outcomes by tailoring treatment plans to individual characteristics and needs	157	100	25	15	5	3.95
Patients reporting higher levels of satisfaction with their healthcare experiences due to the use of AI-driven tools and technologies in diagnosis, treatment, and care delivery	185	68	40	12	0	4.38
The integration of AI-driven chatbots and virtual assistants improved patient engagement and communication	170	97	15	10	10	4.34
The use of AI-driven predictive analytics helped healthcare providers identify patients at high risk of adverse events or complications	200	75	20	7	0	4.54

Table 9 above shows the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications on patient care outcomes and satisfaction, represented with their mean (\bar{X}) respondents; Patients benefit from more accurate and timely diagnoses (4.50), AI-enabled personalized medicine contributed to better patient outcomes by tailoring treatment plans to individual characteristics and needs (3.95), Patients reporting higher levels of satisfaction with their healthcare experiences due to the use of AI-driven tools and technologies in diagnosis, treatment, and care delivery (4.38), The integration of AI-driven chatbots and virtual assistants improved patient engagement and communication (4.34), while majority of the respondents agree that the use of AI-driven predictive analytics helped healthcare providers identify patients at high risk of adverse events or complications (4.54).

4. DISCUSSION

Findings from table 6 showed that, majority with 4.73 means respondents, revealed that technological advancements, such as electronic health records and telemedicine, improve patient care. This agrees with WHO, (2023) who asserted that, technological advancements, such as electronic health records (EHRs) and telemedicine, have improved access to care and streamlined healthcare delivery. These result in decongesting hospital and improved patient-doctors ratio. Additionally, advances in medical treatments and interventions have led to better outcomes for many patients. Also, majority of the respondents with 4.62 mean of respondents, opined that AI is capable of automating repetitive tasks in healthcare, such as transcription and documentation, to save time for healthcare professionals.

More so, majority of the respondents with 5.77 mean response agree that, adoption of Artificial Intelligence has the potential to significantly transform and improve healthcare delivery in various aspects of your organization. This concurs with Topol, (2019) who lament that, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has revolutionized various sectors, including healthcare, by enhancing the quality, efficiency, and accessibility of services. In healthcare, AI technologies are applied in diverse areas such as medical imaging, diagnostics, drug discovery, personalized medicine, and patient management.

Finally, findings from table 9 showed that majority of the respondents with 4.54 mean response agree that the use of AI-driven predictive analytics helped healthcare providers identify patients

at high risk of adverse events or complications. This is in line with Obermeyer et al, (2016) who says AI-driven predictive analytics helped healthcare providers provide valuable insights into a person's risk of developing certain diseases, their response to medications, and potential treatment options.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings, the researcher concluded that attention should be paid to the use of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare Systems as AI is capable of automating repetitive tasks in healthcare, such as transcription and documentation, to save time for healthcare professionals. Artificial Intelligence has the potential to significantly transform and improve healthcare delivery in various aspects of your organization. Artificial Intelligence (AI) has revolutionized various sectors, including healthcare, by enhancing the quality, efficiency, and accessibility of services. In healthcare, AI technologies are applied in diverse areas such as medical imaging, diagnostics, drug discovery, personalized medicine, and patient management.

5.1 Recommendations

In view of the above findings, the following recommendations were made for management of the institution and to the entire health institutions in Kaduna State and Nigeria at large. The following aspects should be improved for the use of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare Systems in the future:

1. Management of health institution should inject more financial resources into the organization in order to adopt the use of Artificial Intelligence in Healthcare Systems to enhance the quality, efficiency, and accessibility of services.
2. The government/management should ensure adequate continuous professional development, collaboration and partnership.
3. They should always ensure adequate training/re-training of staff on the advancement of the ever-changing technological world.

5.2 Limitation of the Study

The researcher encountered two constraints; time for data collection, which helps in building the manuscript. Also, financial constraint hampered the smooth activities of the research work.

5.3 Suggestion for further Studies

It is recommended for further studies to adopt both quantitative and qualitative research approaches in similar studies in Artificial Intelligence (AI) to generate diversified responses from participants.

The use of AI-driven predictive analytics helped healthcare providers identify patients at high risk of adverse events or complications. This is in line with Obermeyer et al, (2016) who says AI-driven predictive analytics helped healthcare providers provide valuable insights into a person's risk of developing certain diseases, their response to medications, and potential treatment options.

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